

THE GREAT NATION - WORKING PAPER

*Submitted as a Citizens' Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)*

Submitted to:

The Republic of the Philippines,
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Submitted by:

Jonelle Peter Muñoz

Date Created: September 26, 2025 to October 12, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17350283

Note: *This document presents a core idea and does not yet constitute a fully drafted proposed law with detailed sections. It is intended as a foundation for further development and refinement in future legislative work.*

The majority of the first 100 Proposed Laws are included in The Great Nation 2025 started on December 9, 2024. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5310407> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5310407>.

Additional proposed laws will be gradually published in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #100

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Strengthening the Notarial System in the Philippines by Requiring Thumbmarks Beside Signatures on All Notarized Documents

(Individual Budget Amendments of All Elective Officials
shall also be documented and notarized with thumbmark)

- September 26, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Proposed Law #100: A Law Strengthening the Notarial System in the Philippines by Requiring Thumbmarks Beside Signatures on All Notarized Documents

All affiant/s, two witnesses, and the lawyer of the notary office must place a thumbmark on the right side of their respective signatures on every page of the notarized document.

Reason for proposing this law:

A notary office, after a person testified under oath before the Senate Blue Ribbon Committee in aid of legislation, produced another affidavit and claimed that they had not notarized the original document.

If the notary office recants its notarization, the thumbmarks of the affiant, lawyer, and two witnesses can then be authenticated by advanced technology.

This can also strengthen and improve the notarial system in the Philippines, given that there have been cases where the lawyer and the required witnesses were not present during the actual notarization.

PROPOSED LAW #101

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All Members of the
Legislative Bodies, such as Senators,
Members of House of the Representatives,
City/Municipal Councilors, and Board Members,
to Explain Their Votes in a Position Paper
of at Least 500 Words

- October 2, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #101: A Law Requiring All Members of the Legislative Bodies, such as Senators, Members of House of the Representatives, City/Municipal Councilors, and Board Members, to Explain Their Votes in a Position Paper of at Least 500 Words

A law requiring Senators to explain their votes in a position paper of at least 500 words. The public may or may not be curious about the rationale behind their voting decisions.

However, public policymakers and lawmakers, as well as some concerned Filipinos, can use these position papers to further advance and strengthen public policy.

If not all legislators can explain their votes verbally, they should at least spend some time writing a position paper to justify their voting decisions.

This proposed law is also applicable to other legislative bodies such as district representatives, city/municipal councilors, and provincial board members.

PROPOSED LAW #102

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring the Public Disclosure of the Individual Budget Insertions and Amendments of All Senators and Members of the House of Representatives for the Past Ten Years

(Also applicable to other local legislative bodies such as
city/municipal councilors and provincial board members)

- October 5, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #102: A Law Requiring the Public Disclosure of the Individual Budget Insertions and Amendments of All Senators and Members of the House of Representatives for the Past Ten (10) Years

There shall be a government website that itemizes all individual budget insertions and amendments made by all Senators and Members of the House of Representatives for the past ten years.

The website shall, at a minimum, include filters by Senator, Member of the House of Representatives, Name of Project, Location of Project (City and Province), Type of Project (e.g., school, hospital, road, flood control, etc.), and Status of the Project (Completed, Incomplete, Substandard, or Ghost).

This proposed law is also applicable to other local legislative bodies such as city/municipal councilors and provincial board members.

Once the government has completed the publication of data for the past ten years, it can then begin publicizing data from the 11th to 20th years in the past.

Presumption of Accountability:

To raise the standard of infrastructure projects, the burden of proof that no irregularities exist shall rest jointly on the politician, the supervising engineer, and the contractor. They share accountability to demonstrate, with verifiable evidence, that the project was executed properly and in accordance with approved standards and budgets.

The Presumption of Innocence applies to all citizens "innocent until proven guilty", as it is a fundamental human rights principle, while the Presumption of Accountability applies to all public officials in the performance of their duties and responsibilities.

PROPOSED LAW #103

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All Journalists to Uphold the Highest Standards of Journalism at All Times

- October 5, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #103: A Law Requiring All Journalists to Uphold the Highest Standards of Journalism at All Times

Rationale:

A journalist in the Philippines, with more than 25 years of experience, decided to publicize the list of budget amendments of ONE senator.

He disclosed that the record came from the Senate. However, HE DID NOT DISCLOSE the budget amendments and insertions of the other twenty-three (23) senators.

According to Senator Panfilo Lacson, individual budget insertions and/or amendments, whatever they may be called depending on one's perspective or definition, can amount to as much as 100 billion pesos.

And yet, this journalist, with at least 25 years of experience, chose to discuss in public only the 3 billion pesos' worth of budget amendments of one senator.

He must have seen the entire list from the Senate, and yet he decided to focus only on the budget of a single senator.

He did not discuss in detail the budgets of the other 23 senators, nor the budget amendments or insertions of all other senators in his past 25 years of journalism experience.

This proposed law will be amended in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #104

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Creating a Special Division Under the Sandiganbayan and the Office of the Ombudsman to Focus on the Silent Transfer of Unexplained Wealth from Public Officials to Their Legal Heirs

(Exemption: Those Wealth Justified by Income Tax Returns)

- October 5, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

~~Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed~~

Proposed Law #104: A Law Creating a Special Division Under the Sandiganbayan and the Office of the Ombudsman to Focus on the Silent Transfer of Unexplained Wealth from Public Officials to Their Legal Heirs

The competent and independent lawyers and accountants of the Special Division shall focus on the silent transfer of unexplained wealth from corrupt public officials to their legal heirs.

Rationale:

Corruption in the Philippines is so systematic and unprecedented in world history that we should not only focus on the public officials themselves but also on their legal heirs.

Important Provision:

Aside from the Certificate Authorizing Registration (CAR) from the BIR, which is a crucial requirement in transferring properties, the legal heirs of all corrupt public officials shall also receive the following:

1. An original certified copy of the first SALN of their parents or grandparents who have served as public officials;
2. The estimated amount of unexplained wealth stolen by their parents or grandparents who have served as public officials;
3. The local and national corruption rankings of their parents or grandparents, as estimated by an independent organization;
4. The estimated opportunity cost caused by the public officials' corruption (e.g., the number of Filipino children deprived of education and a better future, or the number of Filipinos who died due to poor healthcare);

5. A certified true copy of all the income tax returns (ITRs) of their parents and grandparents who have served as public officials;
6. The number of real estate properties owned before and after assuming public office (to be specified by type of property, total area in square meters, etc.).

Amendment to Existing Law:

The unexplained wealth of public officials cannot be inherited by their legal heirs unless proven through all ITRs that such wealth was accumulated in good faith.

The legal heirs of all corrupt public officials shall not inherit the wealth without attending at least a one-month seminar about the greed of their parents and grandparents, and the opportunity costs of such unimaginable greed.

PROPOSED LAW #105

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring the Conduct of Systematic and Transparent Localized Sandiganbayan Public Hearings Involving Public Officials and Contractors in Every City, Municipality, and Province (Prioritizing those with Substandard, Incomplete or Ghost Projects)

- October 10, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #105: A Law Requiring the Conduct of Systematic and Transparent Localized Sandiganbayan Public Hearings Involving Public Officials and Contractor in every City, Municipality and Province

There's one President and one Vice President in the Philippines.

There are 24 Senators, 1,493 Municipal Mayors, 149 City Mayors, 82 Governors, 254 District Representatives, and 64 Party-list Representatives.

In total, there are 2,068 number of high ranking politicians in the Philippines. I exclude the board members, and city/municipal councilors for simplicity of the computation.

If, hypothetically, at least 90% of them are corrupt and have incomplete/substandard/ghost infrastructure projects, and on average it will take three months to have a final Sandiganbayan court decision,

then it would take x number of months or years to put all of the corrupt politicians in jail.

$$2,068 \times 90\% = 1,861$$

x number of months if the cases will be process on SEQUENCE or one case at a time.
One case every three months.

5,583 months or 465 years

While,

x number of months if the cases will be process SIMULTANEOUSLY using systematic and transparent Sandiganbayan Public Hearing in every city, municipality and province.

$$1,493 + 149 + 82 = 1,724 \text{ local Sandiganbayan courts}$$

3 to 6 months only since there are 1,861 high ranking public officials.

The above excludes the DPWH/LGU Engineer and the Contractor of the infrastructure project. It will take many many months before the Philippines can put all corrupt public officials in jail if done in SEQUENCE compared to SIMULTANEOUS (three to six months) if there is a local Sandiganbayan Court in every City, Municipality and Province.

Also, the computation is just a conservative estimate. The three months final court decision is too ideal in the Philippines, unless otherwise institutionalised.

The corruption in the Philippines is systemic and unprecedented in world history. We need a systemic solution.

Empower the existing constitutional bodies such as the Commission on Audit (COA), Ombudsman and Sandiganbayan. Make them highly independent, with the budget automatically allocated to them.

Hire as many lawyers and accountants as possible, in proportion to the estimated number of corrupt public officials.

Then make all hearings public, like the exact transparency in the Blue Ribbon Committee with Facebook and YouTube Live.

All local constituents are invited to every local Sandiganbayan public hearing, so the venue could be open spaces such as gymnasiums and evacuation centers.

PROPOSED LAW #106

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All Politicians, Supervising Engineers, and Contractors to Retrofit Their Respective Substandard Projects and Complete Their Incomplete and Ghost Projects Within twelve (12) Months

(Life sentence shall be imposed on any individual
who fails to complete the respective project they
signed within the prescribed 12-month period)

- October 9, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #106: A Law Requiring All Politicians, Supervising Engineers, and Contractors to Retrofit Their Respective Substandard Projects and Complete Their Incomplete and Ghost Projects Within twelve (12) Months

Proposed Penalty:

Failure to complete any incomplete, substandard, or ghost project within the next 12 months shall result in permanent disqualification from holding any public office.

Furthermore, all assets and properties, except those declared in their first Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth (SALN), shall be automatically transferred to the Republic of the Philippines.

A life sentence shall also be imposed on any individual who fails to complete the respective project they signed within the prescribed 12-month period.

Rationale:

Corruption in the Philippines is unprecedented in world history. It is like a systemic multibillion-peso money heist I once watched on Netflix, where most of the team members appear good in public but are devilish in private. They carefully plan, organize, and strategize how to steal money from poor Filipino children.

Since their crime and actions have been exposed to the public, it is reasonable to require them to complete their projects within a reasonable timeline.

This proposed law is written for Filipino children who are deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed.

PROPOSED LAW #107

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring the Mandatory Reporting of Unexplained Wealth by Immediate Relatives of Corrupt Public Officials and Their Conspirators or Contractors

(Prioritizing those with Substandard, Incomplete or Ghost Projects)

- October 9, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

~~Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed~~

Proposed Law #107: Mandatory Reporting of Unexplained Wealth by Relatives of Corrupt Public Officials and their Contractors

Rationale:

When someone finds money in a public place, the natural action of a good person is to return it to the authorities. If it is proven through evidence that the person did not return the money, the authorities can file a theft case against them.

The same principle should apply to the spouse and immediate family members of politicians, contractors, or public officials.

If they know the whereabouts of unexplained wealth of their relatives who are incumbent or former politicians, public officials, or government contractors, they must report it to the authorities. Failure to do so makes them complicit.

Eating and praying daily with a theft is an insult to those Filipino children who have to work hard so that they can eat and go to school, and to those who have lost their future because of greed.

Important Provisions:

1. Scope - Applies to spouses, parents, siblings, and adult children of politicians, contractors, or public officials.

Covers unexplained wealth, assets, or financial transactions inconsistent with lawful income.

2. Duty to Report - Family members must report any unexplained wealth of their relative to the Ombudsman within 30 days of its discovery.

Knowledge of such wealth without reporting constitutes complicity in corruption. Complicity means "kasangkot".

3. Enforcement - Anti-corruption authorities shall have the power to investigate reported wealth.

Consequences for non-reporting include fines, one-month seminar, and criminal liability.

4. Purpose - To ensure that unexplained or stolen wealth is returned to the public, specially to those children deprived of education and a better future.

To hold family members accountable for knowingly concealing corruption.

To minimize corruption. If public officials, contractors, or politicians know that their family members could one day report them to the Ombudsman, they will think twice before stealing money from the poor.

Legal Basis:

Under Article 308 of the Revised Penal Code, theft is committed by anyone who, having found lost property, fails to deliver it to the local authorities or its owner. This provision establishes an obligation for finders to make reasonable efforts to return lost property.

"Maraming kabataan ang napipilitang mag-dropout sa paaralan dahil sa kakulangan ng scholarship at maayos na edukasyon. Kung pagkatapos ay may daang milyon na unexplained wealth ang asawa, kapatid, nanay, tatay, lolo, o lola mo, hindi mo ba ito irereport sa awtoridad para matulungan ang kapwa mo Pilipino?"

PROPOSED LAW #108

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring the Registry of Deeds and
the Land Registration Authority to
Submit to the Ombudsman and Sandiganbayan
All Unexplained Real Estate Properties
of All Public Officials and Contractors
Involved in Substandard, Incomplete or Ghost Projects

- October 10, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

~~Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed~~

Proposed Law #108: A Law Requiring the Registry of Deeds and Land Registration Authority to Submit to the Ombudsman All Unexplained Real Estate Properties of all Corrupt Public Officials and Their Contractors

This proposed law prioritizes those who have unreasonable increase in real estate properties within a short period of time, particularly within the past five to ten years.

Greedy politicians, public officials, and contractors involved in substandard, incomplete and ghost infrastructure projects shall automatically be included in the list.

Once proven to be unexplained wealth by verifiable evidence, those real estate properties shall be returned to the Republic of the Philippines to fund the construction of schools and provide scholarships for Filipino children.

This can be a good alternative to SALN publications, serving as a database of unexplained wealth directly from the Registry of Deeds and LRA.

This proposed law will be amended in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #109

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Imposing a Penalty of Life Imprisonment and Perpetual Disqualification from Public Office on Those Public Officials Who Have Unexplained Wealth of at Least Ten (10) Million Pesos for Three (3) Consecutive Years

- October 12, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #109: A Law Imposing a Penalty of Life Imprisonment and Perpetual Disqualification from Public Office on Those Public Officials Who Have Unexplained Wealth of at Least Ten (10) Million Pesos for Three (3) Consecutive Years

Important Provision:

Exceptions are those declared in the first SALN, or any wealth justifiable with ITR.

10 Million can be changed to any amount as maybe deemed necessary threshold by highly independent experts.

Within three years after the passage of this law, the public officials have the option to transfer all their unexplained wealth to the Republic of the Philippines, specifically to build schools at a reasonable cost.

If after the three (3) years period, they still do not return their unexplained wealth to the poor Filipino children through the building of schools and providing scholarships, then the penalty of life imprisonment and perpetual disqualification shall be final.

Additionally, all their legal heirs up to the third generation cannot inherit any unexplained wealth unless proven by their parent's and grandparent's ITR.

10 Million is my proposed threshold, it could be lower or higher to be finalized by the future Congress.

I mean, if you have 10 Million in your bank account, why do you need an excess of that? Those are just numbers, unless used for the greater good.

10 Million is a reasonable amount of money to live a comfortable and happy life in the retirement period. Or maybe 5 Million or lower, depending on how frugal a person can be.

Any excess of 10 Million will be an opportunity of a lifetime to many Filipino children.

This proposed law will be amended and completed in the future. I'm optimistic that a wise Filipino president will prioritize this piece of legislation in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #110

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All DPWH and LGU Engineers
to Inspect and Retrofit (When Necessary)
All Public Infrastructure Buildings,
Especially Schools, Which Are Considered
a Second Home by Millions of Filipino Children
(With Automatic Local Budget Allocation Provision)

- October 12, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #110: A Law Requiring All DPWH and LGU Engineers to Inspect and Retrofit (if needed) All Public Infrastructure Buildings, especially Schools, which are considered a second home by millions of Filipino children.

Proposed Penalty: For each child casualty in a specific locality, the highest local DPWH and LGU Engineer shall be the most accountable.

Their one-month salary shall automatically be donated to the immediate family members of the child.

In case of at least five (5) casualties due to poor building construction and inspection, those signatories of the public infrastructure project shall be disallowed to run for public office for six (6) years.

If it is proven by verifiable evidence that the infrastructure projects that caused five (5) casualties are due to corruption or kickbacks, then the politician and DPWH/LGU Engineer involved shall be perpetually disqualified from holding public office.

Their one-month salary shall automatically be donated to the family members of each casualty.

Ideally, there must be at least one DPWH/LGU Engineer accountable for all schools in every three to five barangays. This shall be their additional duty and responsibility, as to be amended in the Local Government Code of 1991.

All Local Chief Executives, such as Mayors and Governors, shall be required to automatically appropriate local budgets once the LGU/DPWH Engineer deems it necessary to retrofit a school building.

This proposed law will be amended in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #111

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All CoA Auditors or Their Designated Spokesperson to Explain All Their Individual Audit Findings to the Public via Facebook or YouTube Live

- October 12, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #111: A Law Requiring All CoA Auditors or Their Designated Spokesperson to Explain All their Individual Audit Findings to the Public via Facebook or YouTube Live.

"Justice delayed is justice denied." The public can't wait for one year or more, or worst, 10 years for a final Sandiganbayan court ruling. The politician, contractor, or public official involved will keep stealing again every year if there is no final ruling within the first year.

Exception:

If the irregularities involve at least Php 50 million, the CoA auditors or their designated spokesperson shall be required to explain it to the public via Facebook or YouTube Live within three (3) months.

The Php 50 million limit can be changed to Php 25 million or any amount not lower than Php 500,000.

Important Provisions:

Thirty (30) days after the CoA auditors or their designated spokesperson make a live Facebook or YouTube video, the involved politicians, contractors, or engineers shall be required to explain their innocence with verifiable evidence to the public via Facebook or YouTube Live.

According to the 1987 Constitution, "Public office is a public trust. Public officers and employees must, at all times, be accountable to the people, serve them with utmost responsibility, integrity, loyalty, and efficiency; act with patriotism and justice, and lead modest lives."

All COA auditors are accountable to the people, not to politicians. Your reports must be explained and be known to the public. You spend the whole year gathering evidence, inspecting properties, services, and goods, and writing the final audit report, only to wait by luck or by chance, to see whether it will be forwarded by the Ombudsman to the Sandiganbayan?

To all CoA auditors, "If you believe there is an anomaly, you can explain it to the public tomorrow morning or afternoon. Thank you in advance."

Greedy public officials and/or contractors who often steal money from poor Filipino children will think twice before doing it again, because independent CoA auditors will be required by this law to explain their wrongdoings to the public.

This proposed law will be amended and completed with proper sections. I'm optimistic that a wise Filipino president will prioritize this piece of legislation in the future.